

8T – The Operators Fiasco

O Manor

October 19, 2021

Abstract:

The author analyzes the weakness in the idea of operators of creation and destruction in the QFT formalism, using the new framework of varying manifolds. It is possible to cut by half the number of operators needed to describe nature. It also allows to deem the anti-matter operators as irrelevant and problematic, as they indicate high state of energy which is against nature tendency to each the lowest energy state, the author elaborate on the alternative to this idea. Second part of the article is presenting a way to combine spin operators with the coupling constant series.

Introduction

One of the major pillars of the QFT formalism is based upon a sequence of operators, which represent creation and destruction of particles. By analyzing from several angles using the recent developments of variational manifolds, it become evident that the operator formalism is problematic. The first problem was already briefly mentioned in previous papers and is the following, if for each particle matter created there exist an anti-matter, would mean that they exist in equal amounts. Define the set of operators and two scalar coefficients.

$$\lambda = \{a(t), a^\dagger(t), K_1, K_2\}$$

$$K_2 a(t) = K_1 a^\dagger(t)$$

$$K_2 a(t) a^\dagger(t) K_1 = 0$$

Based upon cosmological observation the ratio is majorly unbalanced toward matter.

$$K_2 a(t) \gg a^\dagger(t) K_1$$

Such an idea also means that there exist constant amount of high-energy release in space-time due to pairs of creation and destruction, which means that the universe in QFT formalism cannot reach lowest energy state, but rather the opposite due to those vanishing pairs it is in the highest state of energy.

$$\langle K_2 | K_1 \rangle = 0$$

QFT physicists tried to those vanishing pairs to explain "dark energy" they created the biggest mismatch between an idea an observational value, by magnitude of several tens of zeros, solidifying the problem with this idea. That is not a case against anti-matter, as we know it does exist, the subject matter in hand is about creating a setting in which matter creation does not interfere with the stationarity condition of the universe. In the new framework of varying curvature, the objective is easily within reach, as matter pairs in such way that does not allow arbitrary curvature to manifest, the stationarity condition of the manifold is preserved. Additional side point is assuming nature itself is Lagrangian oriented, why would it bother to create a set of elements, and then create an inverse set of elements, of the same magnitude, just to destroy them both? In other words, why create two sets of elements instead of just one? The new framework of variational curvature has just one set of elements, which does not interfere with the stationarity condition as it vanishes into zero, without the need for Anti-matter. In the 8T, the idea of vanishing curvature spikes into matter:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 ; Z = 1$$

In QFT,

$$K_2 a(t) a^\dagger(t) K_1 = 0 ; Z = 2$$

Where Z denoting the number of sets. The second set of elements assuming to contain an infinite number of elements, which will require nature to much more work, which again a indication of theoretical fiasco. A third point is the following, if the operator idea was correct than it would require a 'constant care' to ensure the number of operators is equal both direction. Such an idea is than is in contradiction to the randomness and spontaneous nature of nature, as we are familiar with it. That is that the requirement of both operators to be equal at all times is synonymous with magic, we would lose the randomness and the spontaneous features of nature, the operators must be aligned at both temporal and spatial dimensions. Such restriction does not exist in the 8T.

$$(K_2 = K_1) \forall \mu$$

$$\mu = (\nabla^2, t_n, s_n)$$

The succession of operators being created and annihilated is troublesome notion wise and can be infinitely long.

$$\left(a(t) a^\dagger(t) \right)_1 \dots \left(a(t) a^\dagger(t) \right)_n$$

For those reasons, it is possible to claim that the operator idea is problematic. Reader may rightfully ask about the suggested alternative. The 8T is suggesting the following. Matter and anti-matter are not equal in creation, which is preserving the stationarity condition. Matter is being created across the manifold, it is manifested in such way that no curvature is allowed da facto. Energy is not preserved, but the stationarity of the manifold is. Instead of two sets of operators, there exist just one, which summed in one term instead by infinite sequence. Its full proof Lagrangian oriented, as the number of elements reduced by a factor of one infinity, it does not involve high energy or anti-matter, which will invoke the manifold far from stationary, and this term it still vanishing to zero, all in one without anti-matter. It also allows the spontaneous nature of nature to manifested as those are **arbitrary** variations rather than directed and pre-calculated two-fold set of operators equal in size. One final point, if that idea of equal two-sets of operators was in fact correct, than matter, stars and galaxies would not have been existed in the first place. If one impose a restriction of that sort, one must specify in which time segments in applies. QFT does not tell from when temporal segment it becomes valid which is another problem.

Spin Orientations

$$\left(\mathbf{2}e^- * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_{V\mu} + e^-_{\mu} \right) + \gamma_{\mu} = 30:128:850:9254 \dots$$

The Primorial, which has several forms including a unique spin, form which led to the following classification:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $N = 2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

The missing art is the following, the primorial does not provide the actual direction of spin propagation in three dimensions. As a result, one must consider the three-direction combination as a mean to present the orientation of the spin:

$$\theta: (\phi_x + \phi_y + \phi_z) \in t_n \in s_n$$

That is, spin orientation taken for some arbitrary time, for some arbitrary manifold. The new arrow is:

$$\theta: e^-_{\mu} \rightarrow e^-_{\mu\theta}$$

$$\theta: \gamma_{\mu} \rightarrow \gamma_{\mu\theta}$$

The second power will given by the joint terms in the subscript each of the spin operator is joining the diverging Laplacian such that:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{g}}{\partial x_n^2}(\phi_x) + \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{g}}{\partial y_n^2}(\phi_y) + \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{g}}{\partial z_n^2}(\phi_z) \in t_n$$

$$(\phi_x^2 + \phi_y^2 + \phi_z^2) = 1$$

The purpose of the new combined term is not only to describe the curvature diverging on the manifold but also to allocate in addition the spin components for each spatial coordinate such that putting net and spin under one frame.

$$\theta: \left(\mathbf{2}e^- * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_{V\mu} + e^-_{\mu} \right) + \gamma_{\mu} \rightarrow \left(\mathbf{2}e^-_{(\mu\theta)} * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_{V(\mu\theta)} + e^-_{\mu\theta} \right) + \gamma_{\mu\theta}$$

References

[1] O. Manor. "8T – The Grand Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

M. Okad's Theory